

On a multiple crack order parameter phase-field model accounting for mechanical jump conditions

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Motivation and recently addressed topics

Motivation

- Materials with complex morphologies and high contrast in material parameters
- Few phasefield models for crack propagation in heterogeneous systems exist

Schöllner et al. (2022) Fig.13

Recently addressed topics

- Multiple crack order parameters (MCOP) multiphase-field model introduced in Schöllner et al. (2022)
- Extension of MCOP model to account for mechanical jump conditions in Schöllner et al. (2023)

Schöllner et al. (2023) Fig.1

Schöllner et al. (2023) Fig.3

Acknowledgement and recent publications

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Recent publications

Prahs, Reder, Schneider, Nestler, Int. J. Mech. Sci. (2023), currently in production

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